

Reliable in-Vehicle perception and decision-making in complex environmental conditions

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D.7.3: Intermediate EVENTS Communication, Dissemination, and social awareness

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Executive Summary

Effective communication, dissemination, and social awareness processes play a crucial role in ensuring the success of a project as ambitious and visionary as EVENTS. Supported by the European Union's Horizon Europe Framework Programme, EVENTS aims to establish a robust perception and decision-making system for Connected and Automated Vehicles (CAVs) to navigate various "events" on the horizon, presenting challenges that must be addressed for the safe and reliable automation of driving in such scenarios.

This document, designated as *D.7.3: Intermediate EVENTS Communication, Dissemination, and Social Awareness*, is considered a dynamic document linked to Task 7.1: EVENTS Communication & Dissemination and Task 7.4: Social Innovation & Gender Equality within Work Package WP7: Outreach.

The primary purpose of this document is to offer a comprehensive overview of the communication, dissemination, and scientific activities undertaken by EVENTS consortium partners from the commencement of the project until M18 (February 2024). The overarching goal of these activities is to enhance awareness and outreach regarding EVENTS results, outputs, and technical work conducted in the initial eighteen months among various target audiences.

More specifically, the report provides quantitative information on the status of EVENTS communication and dissemination channels, tools, and methods, scientific activities conducted, participation in prominent conferences and events, as well as details on clustering and networking activities.

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Abbreviations & Acronyms

Abbreviation / acronym	Description
CA	Consortium Agreement
CAVs	Connected and Automated Vehicles
CCAM	Cooperative, Connected and Automated Mobility
CINEA	European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency
Dx.x	Deliverable x.x
DoA	Decision of Actions
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
HE	Horizon Europe
HRB	Horizon Results Booster
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
M01, M02 etc.	Month 1, Month 2, etc
ORE	Open Research Europe
PO	Project Officer
PU	Public Use
R&D	Research & Development
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the document

The current deliverable, D7.3: Intermediate EVENTS Communication, Dissemination, and social awareness, is the first update of D7.1 EVENTS Communication, Dissemination, and social awareness, which constitutes a key reference document for all the communication, dissemination, and social awareness activities to be implemented within WP7 of EVENTS project and it is intended as a living document through the project's lifetime.

This document contains all communication, dissemination, scientific and activities performed, attended, organised, and conducted from the beginning of the project until M18 (February 2024) by EVENTS consortium partners.

This deliverable has been prepared and delivered by SEAB, as lead beneficiary of the Work Package 7 'Outreach', towards recording the contributions from all EVENTS project partners.

1.2 Intended readership

D7.3: Intermediate EVENTS Communication, Dissemination, and social awareness is a public deliverable, addressed not only to the consortium members, but also to any interested reader (i.e., Public (PU) dissemination level).

It is primarily written for the European Commission (EC), Project Officer (PO) and the consortium members of the EVENTS project as a useful information hub of EVENTS communication, dissemination, and social awareness activities.

Nevertheless, special effort and focus have been, also, given on making this report a stand-alone comprehensible document for the general public.

1.3 Document Structure

Section 1 introduces the purpose of the document, the intended readership, and the document structure.

Section 2 provides a status description of EVENTS communication and dissemination channels, tools, and means.

Section 3 presents the EVENTS scientific activities that have been conducted by M18.

Section 4 summarises EVENTS attendance and participation in related events, conferences, seminars, workshops, and exhibitions, by M18.

Section 5 describes the performed clustering and networking activities during the first 18 months of the project.

Section 6 highlights, in general, the social awareness perspective.

Section 7 analyses the status of the evaluation and monitoring processes of the EVENTS communication and dissemination activities during the first eighteen months of the project duration.

Finally, section 8 summarizes the concluding remarks of *D.7.3: Intermediate EVENTS Communication, Dissemination, and social awareness*.

2. EVENTS Communication Kit (Channels, Tools & Means)

A variety of channels have been designed, created, and are actively used since the beginning of the project, to effectively flow EVENTS information, create awareness and reach out to the targeted audiences, by taking into consideration the specific characteristics and needs of each targeted group. The following list of the available communication channels, tools and means shows the already defined kit of transmitting the information produced within EVENTS project and depicts their current status and progress within the first eighteen months of the project duration.

2.1 Online Channels

The EVENTS project online channels include the project's website and the social media accounts.

2.1.1 Project website

EVENTS website constitutes the backbone of the project's communication and dissemination activities. The website serves as a point of reference for all different users and stakeholders and provides up-to-date information in a simple way about the project objectives, the proposed areas of work, the use cases, the consortium, project results, related articles, and project material (e.g., public deliverables, open access publications, newsletters, dissemination & presentation material, news etc.). The website was officially launched on M01 (September 2022) and became fully functional, on M03 (November 2022) including several sections (Figure 1) (e.g. Home, About, Consortium, Material Hub, News & Events etc). It can be accessed through the following URL: <https://www.events-project.eu/>.

Figure 1 Indicative screenshot of EVENTS website

According to EVENTS website analytics shown in Figure 2, the total number of users has reached 1.4k users¹, within the first 18 months of the project, while the website views has reached 4911 views, within the same period. Also, the average session² duration is approximately 01:18 min and the total number of sessions, within the recorded period, is 358.146 sessions.

Figure 2 EVENTS website analytics

2.1.2 Social Media accounts

EVENTS has been maintaining three social media accounts on Twitter/X, LinkedIn, and YouTube since the beginning of the project on M01 (September 2022), in order to maximize dissemination of the project results and engagement. All social media accounts have been developed and maintained by SEAB. All social media accounts are connected to the project's website and the visibility of all the accounts is continuously monitored and regularly evaluated using both quantitative measures obtained by its platform's analytics as well as, qualitative measures towards evaluating any type of comment that may be received. Related to partner's activities content announcements, have been created and fertilised EVENTS social media accounts.

2.1.2.1 Twitter/X account

EVENTS Twitter/X account (@EVENTSproject22) is used for presenting the latest news about the project with regular updates and photo material from EVENTS partners'.

¹ According to Google Analytics [1], "Total users" is the total number of people who visited EVENTS site in a specified date range.

² A session in Google Analytics is a group of interactions recorded when a user visits the website within a given period.

This includes activities during meetings, workshops, and events, as well as retweets from related twitter accounts of similar initiatives and projects. Besides, all EVENTS partners are responsible for increasing the awareness of this tool, by creating linkages to their accounts and by providing SEAB with relevant content and contributions related to their achievements.

EVENTS Twitter/X account counts 104 followers (up to M18). According to the Twitter/X analytics (Figure 3 & Figure 4), EVENTS Tweets earned an average of 231 impressions over the last 91-day period. EVENTS twitter account can be accessed in the following link: <https://twitter.com/EVENTSproject22>.

Figure 3 Twitter/X analytics on the impressions over a 91-day period

Figure 4 Twitter/X analytics on the impressions of two indicative posts

2.1.2.2 LinkedIn account

EVENTS LinkedIn account (@EVENTSproject22) has been created to share relevant content, connect with already established prominent groups and transmit the project’s insights, concept, vision, and progress. EVENTS LinkedIn account gathers 138 followers (up to M18).

According to the LinkedIn analytics, over the last 12 months (February 2023-February 2024) the organic impressions have been reached approximately 66 impressions by M18 (Figure 5). EVENTS LinkedIn page account can be accessed here: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/eventsproject22/>.

Figure 5 Organic impressions over the last 12 months (February 2023-February 2024)

2.1.2.3 YouTube account

EVENTS project maintains, also, a YouTube channel, aimed at sharing videos related to the project achievements, in the context of its dissemination and communication procedures. YouTube is considered a valuable channel for showcasing the project’s general video, the project’s use cases, as well as other audio visual activities. EVENTS YouTube account can be accessed here: <https://www.youtube.com/@eventsproject>.

Project video, as well as, any other audiovisual material produced within the project, will be available in this channel. Also, any recorded partner’s activity from related conferences, events, seminars, webinars etc, will be also available under this channel.

2.2 Dissemination Tools

EVENTS’s dissemination tools, either in hard copy or in digital format, are in line with the overall EVENTS communication strategy ensuring the achievement of the project’s

objectives and the effective engagement of the interested target audiences. Such material is always consistent with EVENTS brand identity and the communication guidelines provided by the European Commission (EC)[2].

Dissemination tools, as part of the project’s communication kit, consist of: i) the project’s fact sheet, ii) the overall presentation, iii) the brochure, iv) the poster, v) the roll up banner and vi) the project video. The material has been presented, in detail, as part of D7.1 EVENTS Communication, Dissemination, and social awareness.

The aforementioned material (except for the project video, which has not yet been released) has been updated, in M16 (December 2023), to include the new, recently joint, partner’s details (PERCIVAI).

EVENTS general project video is planned to be officially launched after M18 with the aim to gain more attention and spread significant awareness on the project activities. The plan is to develop a 3 to 4 minutes’ video that would make use of visual, sound and text elements to introduce the project and visually explains the project’s concept to non-technical audiences and the public. This general video will remark the project’s vision and objectives, its concept, the use cases, as well as the expected project impact. The project video will be produced in English, and it will be disseminated via EVENTS social media, as well as it will be posted in the project’s website and uploaded on EVENTS YouTube channel. It is expected to be disseminated by all project partners, using various means of dissemination.

2.3 Means

2.3.1 EVENTS newsletters

EVENTS website provides the opportunity to its visitors to sign up and receive a regular newsletter (Figure 6). EVENTS e-newsletters constitute an electronic mean of distributing project findings and news, implemented activities as well as upcoming actions. Newsletters are sent to the newsletter subscribers via email, but they are also made available in electronic format in EVENTS website (through Material Hub, Newsletter section) and on EVENTS social media accounts on Twitter and LinkedIn via related posts. The number of subscribers up to M18 is 88 subscribed members. The content of the e-newsletters is based on the continuous progress of the project and aims at informing the interested audiences and stakeholders about the project’s key outcomes and results.

Figure 6 EVENTS e-newsletter subscription functionality

Two e-newsletters have already been launched during the first 18 months of the project, and they are presented in Table 1 (and Figure 7) below:

Table 1 EVENTS e-newsletters

EVENTS e-newsletters	
EVENTS 1st e-newsletter	https://mailchi.mp/314fab5fe893/events-e-newsletter-issue-1?e=86461681e3
EVENTS 2nd e-newsletter	https://mailchi.mp/6f5130995fa2/events-e-newsletter-second-issue?e=86461681e3

Figure 7 Indicative screenshots from e-newsletter 1 (left) and e-newsletter 2 (right)

2.3.2 EVENTS partners interview series

EVENTS partners' interview series have been voted, at the end of the first project year (M12), to be in the form of written interview article. The official release of the first articles is planned for M18 and onwards with main objective to reach out targeted groups of relevant stakeholders and raise awareness on the activities each partner is involved.

Guidelines, along with indicative release schedule, have been prepared by SEAB and were distributed, in advance, among the project partners. All produced fiches will be available in EVENTS website, and they will be spread, also, through relevant posts on EVENTS social media accounts.

2.3.3 EVENTS press activities

Press releases play a significant role in highlighting the successes and advancements made by the project partners. Thus, since the beginning of the project, EVENTS team has produced several press releases, presented in the following Table 2.

EVENTS press activities have been made available on EVENTS website, in the material hub, under Media Centre section.

Table 2 EVENTS press activities

EVENTS Press Activities
EVENTS Kick-off press release EVENTS kick-off meeting in Athens, <u>September 2022</u> , SEAB Clipping 1: https://seability.eu/2022/09/09/events-kick-off-meeting-in-athens/
EVENTS Kick-off press release EVENTS: a new HORIZON project officially launched, <u>September 2022</u> , ICCS Clipping 1: https://i-sense.iccs.gr/news/14382/
EVENTS Kick-off press release ICCS & SEAB participate in EVENTS project, <u>September 2022</u> , ICCS, SEAB Clipping 1: https://www.kathimerini.gr/society/562118311/ochimata-choris-odigo-ena-vima-pio-konta-me-ti-symvoli-toy-emp/ Clipping 2: https://www.eea.gr/arthra-eea/events-aytomatopoiimeni-odigisi-prepei-na-eggyithoyme-oti-i-aytomatopoiimeni-odigisi-einai-asfalis/ Clipping 3: https://www.reporter.gr/Oles-oi-eidhseis/542960-Events-Neo-eyrwpaiko-ergo-gia-th-dieykolynsh-ths-aytomaths-odhghshs Clipping 4: https://ecopress.gr/eb-neo-evropaiko-ergo-events-apo-to-episef/ Clipping 5: https://www.gocar.gr/news/feed/41508,EMP_aytonomh_odhghsh_Eyrwph.html Clipping 6: https://www.supply-chain.gr/%CE%B5%CF%85%CF%81%CF%89%CF%80%CE%B1%CF%8A%CE%BA%CF%8C-%CE%AD%CF%81%CE%B3%CE%BF-events-%CE%AD%CE%BD%CE%B1-%CE%B2%CE%AE%CE%BC%CE%B1-%CF%80%CE%B9%CE%BF-%CE%BA%CE%BF%CE%BD%CF%84%CE%AC-%CF%83%CF%84/2-391/ Clipping 7: https://neatora.gr/episey-emp-events-ena-vima-pio-konta-stin-axiopisti-aytomatopoiimeni-odigisi-se-diskoles-odikes-synt-515179.html Clipping 8: https://www.taxidromos.gr/topic/4350060/ellada-sintonizei-ergo-autonomi-odigisi.html

3. EVENTS scientific activities

EVENTS team produces scientific material and other contributions for the technical literature and dedicated high impact journals with the aim to share the project progress and research findings with the scientific community. The goal of the scientific material within EVENTS is to advance science, by publishing original empirical and theoretical work developed within the project.

Each scientific publication is in accordance and in compliance with the EC rules on Open Access and adheres to the Open Access guidelines [3]. EVENTS will guarantee Open Access (following the GA guidelines of the Annex 5: Article 17) to every EVENTS publication (towards sustaining also either self-archiving / 'Green' open access or open access publishing / 'gold' open access for both the publication itself and its metadata) and this will be ensured for all interested stakeholder communities, mainly through the project’s public gateways (EVENTS online channels) and through the use of the EU innovative open access publishing services (e.g., Open Research Europe (ORE) Platform, European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), OpenAIRE etc.). These services will assist the EVENTS partners to overcome difficulties that arise from obstacles towards open access of project results that occur from publishers’ policy (e.g., embargo period).

The EVENTS team has worked since the early beginning of the project on the production of relevant scientific material based on EVENTS achievements seeking to improve visibility of the project on a more solid basis. EVENTS, also, maintains an indicative list (calendar) of relevant scientific journals, to facilitate partners towards the submission of scientific papers (included in D7.1).

A detailed description of the scientific activities that have been completed until M18 of the project is provided in the following paragraphs.

3.1 Conference Publications

Table 3 below outlines the conference publications of the EVENTS team, between M01-M18, in prominent conferences.

Table 3 EVENTS conference publication between M01-M18

Title	Authors	Event	Publication date	Doi
Pedestrian Environment Model for Automated Driving	Adrian Holzbock*, Alexander Tsaregorodtsev*, and Vasileios Belagiannis° (* Ulm University, ° Friedrich-Alexander-Universität	26th IEEE International Conference on Intelligent Transportation Systems -ITSC 2023	<u>TBU</u>	<u>TBU</u>

	Erlangen-Nürnberg)			
Adaptive Patched Grid Mapping	Thomas Wodtko, Thomas Griebel, and Michael Buchholz (all Ulm University)		<u>TBU</u>	<u>TBU</u>
Introspection of 2D Object Detection using Processed Neural Activation Patterns in Automated Driving Systems	Hakan Yekta Yatbaz, Mehrdad Dianati, Konstantinos Koufos and Roger Woodman (all from WMG)	International Conference on Computer Vision- ICCV	October 2023	https://openaccess.thecvf.com/content/ICCV2023W/BRAVO/html/Yatbaz_Introspection_of_2D_Object_Detection_Using_Processed_Neural_Activation_Patterns_ICCV_2023_paper.html
Online Performance Assessment of Multi-Sensor Kalman Filters Based on Subjective Logic	Thomas Griebel, Jonas Heinzler, Michael Buchholz, and Klaus Dietmayer	26th International Conference on Information Fusion 2023	August 2023	http://dx.doi.org/10.18725/OPARU-51054 https://dx.doi.org/10.23919/FUSION52260.2023.10224188
The Fast Product Multi-Sensor Labeled Multi-Bernoulli Filter	Charlotte Hermann, Martin Herrmann, Thomas Griebel, Michael Buchholz, and Klaus Dietmayer		August 2023	http://dx.doi.org/10.18725/OPARU-51053 https://dx.doi.org/10.23919/FUSION52260.2023.10224189
Track Classification for Random Finite Set Based Multi-Sensor Multi-Object Tracking	Alexander Scheible, Thomas Griebel, Martin Herrmann, Charlotte Hermann, Michael Buchholz	Combined SDF and IEEE MFI Conference	November 2023	10.1109/SDFMFI59545.2023.10361438 https://dx.doi.org/10.1109/SDF-MFI59545.2023.10361438
Fuzzy logic based decision-making for urban platooning on urban roundabout scenarios	Asier Arizala, Gorka Alonso, Joshue Perez, Asier Zubizarreta	ROBOT 2023	November 2023	<u>TBU</u>

3.2 Journal publications

Table 4 below outlines the Journal submission of the EVENTS team, between M01-M18, in prominent scientific journals.

Table 4 EVENTS journal submissions between M01-M18

Title	Authors	Journal	Publication date	Doi
Run-time Introspection of 2D Object Detection in Automated Driving Systems Using Learning Representations	Hakan Yekta Yatbaz, Mehrdad Dianati, Konstantinos Koufos and Roger Woodman	IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Vehicles	<u>TBU (under review)</u>	<u>TBU</u>

4. EVENTS Participation in Events & Conferences

One of the project’s significant dissemination activities is the consortium participation (physical or virtual) in external conferences, workshops, seminar, webinars, and other third-party events via presentations.

Up to month 18, EVENTS partners have been actively engaged and contributed to the communication of EVENTS’s vision and concept, as well as in the dissemination of its findings and outcomes at a plethora of conferences, workshops, seminars and webinars via presentations, constructive discussions, and posters, towards facilitating, also, the connection with the stakeholder’s community. Most of these events constituted a great opportunity for communicating EVENTS’s concept and objectives, disseminating its findings and achieving a higher outreach of the project.

It is also worth mentioning that from the beginning of the project a calendar of events and conferences (included in D7.1) that are considered as valuable opportunities for the project has been created and is regularly updated mainly by WP7 team and by the consortium partners. EVENTS partners are regularly informed through monthly emails about upcoming key opportunities, so they will be able to benefit from them.

4.1 Conference events

The following Table 5, highlights and presents the events that EVENTS partners attended during the first eighteen-month period and includes information about the date, location, and the lead partnership of each dissemination activity as well as the title of presentation and an indicative description along with the corresponding announcement link, accompanied by the presentation material, on EVENTS website.

Table 5 EVENTS Conference events

Date	Event	Location	Title of presentation	Lead Partner	Description (if available)/url
25.10.2022	Connected, Cooperative & Automated mobility (CCAM) event	Brussels, Belgium	EVENTS project on CCAM	ICCS	Presentation was focused on highlighting the key facts, objectives and impact of EVENTS project, and how the project is linked to the CCAM Partnership’s Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA). https://www.events-project.eu/news-title-1/
22-24.05.2023	15th ITS European Congress	Lisbon, Portugal	Challenges of multi modal ML-based perception development & testing for automated	ICCS	SIS 60: Challenges of multi modal ML-based perception development & testing for automated driving applications https://www.events-

			driving applications		project.eu/15th-its-european-congress-22-24-05-2023/
28-31.08.2023	ITS Australia Summit 2023	Melbourne, Australia	Generation of training datasets for ML methods for autonomous vehicles from simulations	ICCS	Presentation was focused on the generation of training datasets for ML methods for autonomous vehicles from simulations https://www.events-project.eu/its-australia-summit-2023-28-31-08-2023/
24-28.09.2023	26th IEEE International Conference on Intelligent Transportation Systems -ITSC 2023	Bilbao, Bizkaia, Spain	Generation of training datasets for ML methods for autonomous vehicles from simulations	ICCS	EVENTS participated in an Industrial Session Proposal entitled: Next-gen mobility planning https://www.events-project.eu/26th-ieee-international-conference-on-intelligent-transportation-systems-itsc-2023-24-28-09-2023/
			Pedestrian Environment Model for Automated Driving	UULM	UULM team delivered two presentations on Pedestrian Environment Model for Automated Driving and on the Adaptive Patched Grid Mapping https://www.events-project.eu/26th-ieee-international-conference-on-intelligent-transportation-systems-itsc-2023-24-28-09-2023/
			Adaptive Patched Grid Mapping	UULM	
27-30.06.2023	26th International Conference on Information Fusion 2023	Charleston, SC, USA	Online Performance Assessment of Multi-Sensor Kalman Filters Based on Subjective Logic	UULM	UULM team delivered a presentation on Online Performance Assessment of Multi-Sensor Kalman Filters Based on Subjective Logic https://www.events-project.eu/26th-international-conference-on-information-fusion-27-30-06-2023/
27-30.06.2023	26th International Conference on Information Fusion 2023	Charleston, SC, USA	The Fast Product Multi-Sensor Labeled Multi-Bernoulli Filter	UULM	UULM team delivered a presentation on The Fast Product Multi-Sensor Labeled Multi-Bernoulli Filter https://www.events-project.eu/26th-international-conference-on-information-fusion-27-30-06-2023/
22-24.11.2023	ROBOT 2023	University of Coimbra, Portugal	Fuzzy logic based decision-making for urban platooning on urban	TECNALIA	TECNALIA team delivered a presentation on Fuzzy logic based decision-making for urban platooning on urban roundabout scenarios https://www.events-

			roundabout scenarios		project.eu/robot-2023-22-14-11-2023/
27-29.11.2023	IEEE SDF-MFI Conference	Bonn, Germany	Track Classification for Random Finite Set Based Multi-Sensor Multi-Object Tracking	UULM	UULM team won third place in the best student paper award https://www.events-project.eu/ieee-sdf-mfi-conference-27-29-11-2023/
05-07.02.2024	Conference on results from road transport research #RTR2024	Brussels, Belgium	Reliable in-Vehicle Perception and decision-making in complex environmental conditions (EVENTS)	ICCS	ICCS team delivered a presentation of EVENTS project https://www.events-project.eu/rtr-conference-2024-05-07-02-2024/

4.2 Workshops, Seminars, Webinars

The following Table 6, presents the workshops, seminars and webinars, that EVENTS partners either organized or attended until M18, including information about the date, location, and the lead partnership of each dissemination activity as well as the workshop/seminar/webinar theme and an indicative description along with the corresponding announcement link, accompanied by the presentation material, on EVENTS website.

Table 6 EVENTS Workshops/Seminars/Webinars

Date	Event	Location	Workshop theme	Lead Partner	Description (if available)/url
02-06.10.2023	International Conference on Computer Vision-ICCV	Paris, France	Robustness and Reliability of Autonomous Vehicles in the Open-world	WMG	A poster presented was the result of a homonymous paper, https://www.events-project.eu/iccv/

4.3 Exhibitions/Booths

The following Table 7, presents the exhibitions and booths, that EVENTS partners either organized or attended until M18, including information about the date and partners involved, the type of dissemination activity and the corresponding announcement link, accompanied by the presentation material, on EVENTS website.

Table 7 EVENTS Exhibitions/Booths

Date	Event	Partners involved	Type of dissemination activity	Link
07-08.12.2022	8th ITS Hellas Conference	SEAB	SEAB showcased the EVENTS project in its booth	https://www.events-project.eu/8th-its-hellas-conference-07-08-12-2022/
15.02.2023	RTR conference 2023	ICCS	EVENTS networking at EC Stand	https://www.events-project.eu/events-networking-at-ec-stand-in-rtr-2023-14-16-02-2023/
03-04.05.2023	4th European Conference on Connected and Automated Driving – EUCAD 2023	ICCS, APTIV, TECHNALIA	EVENTS dissemination material on CCAM Stand	https://www.events-project.eu/4th-european-conference-on-connected-and-automated-driving-eucad-2023-03-04-05-2023/
22-24.05.2023	15th ITS European Congress	ICCS	EVENTS dissemination material on ICCS booth	https://www.events-project.eu/15th-its-european-congress-22-24-05-2023/
13-15.06.2023	ADAS & Autonomous Vehicle Technology Expo 2023	WMG	EVENTS dissemination material on WMG booth	https://www.events-project.eu/adas-autonomous-vehicle-technology-expo-13-15-06-2023/
06-08.09.2023	Driving Simulation Conference Europe 2023	WMG	EVENTS dissemination material on WMG booth	https://www.events-project.eu/driving-simulation-conference-europe-2023-06-08-09-2023/
09-17.09.2023	87th Thessaloniki International Fair (TIF)	ICCS	EVENTS dissemination material on ICCS booth	https://www.events-project.eu/87th-international-exhibition-of-thessaloniki-09-17-09-2023/

4.4 Other activities

The following Table 8, presents other activities that EVENTS was showcased between M01-M18.

Table 8 EVENTS Other activities

Date	Type of activity	Description (if available)/url
09.02.2023	EVENTS on CORDIS EU page	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101069614
03.05.2023	EVENTS on CINEA brochure for CCAM	https://cinea.ec.europa.eu/publications/towards-cooperative-connected-and-automated-mobility_en

5. EVENTS Clustering & Networking activities

EVENTS project aims at strengthening relationships with the entire community involved in the automotive domain, which is made up of different types of actors. The identification and interaction with related projects, and any thematic cluster projects added to the stakeholders' community, are of crucial importance.

EVENTS clustering and networking activities with existing initiatives, projects and stakeholders have been identified and organized to exploit synergies in terms of content sharing, exchange of good practices and joint dissemination for maximizing impact networking thanks to external events.

5.1 Clustering activities

In the context of EVENTS clustering activities, several joint activities have taken place in collaboration with other EU projects during the first 18 months of the project. More specifically, the following Table 9, summarizes the activities that have been conducted jointly by EVENTS and other EU, national and international research projects.

Table 9 EVENTS clustering activities with research projects

Joint activity	Project	Description (if available)/url
1 paper entitled " <u>Adaptive Patched Grid Mapping</u> " submitted in 26th IEEE International Conference on Intelligent Transportation Systems -ITSC 2023	This paper was jointly prepared within EVENTS and U-Shift II projects (U-Shift II is funded by the State Ministry of Economic Affairs Baden-Württemberg (project U-Shift II, AZ 3-433.62-DLR/60))	https://www.events-project.eu/26th-ieee-international-conference-on-intelligent-transportation-systems-itsc-2023-24-28-09-2023/
1 paper entitled " <u>The Fast Product Multi-Sensor Labeled Multi-Bernoulli Filter</u> " submitted in 26th International Conference on Information Fusion 2023	The paper was jointly prepared within EVENTS and LUKAS project (national project with following information: Verbundprojekt: LUKAS - Lokales Umfeldmodell für das kooperative, automatisierte Fahren in komplexen Verkehrssituationen; Teilvorhaben: Infrastrukturseite Datenverarbeitung und kooperative Handlungsplanung / BMWi / 19A20004F), as well as UNICARagil project (national project with following information: Verbundprojekt: Disruptive modulare Architektur für agile, autonome Fahrzeugkonzepte - UNICARagil -; Teilvorhaben: Generische Sensormodule und automatisierte Umgebungswahrnehmung sowie Entwicklung eines autonomen Lieferfahrzeugs / BMBF / 16EMO0290	https://www.events-project.eu/26th-international-conference-on-information-fusion-27-30-06-2023/
1 paper entitled " <u>Track Classification for Random Finite Set Based Multi-Sensor Multi-Object Tracking</u> "	The authors are involved in different projects (on EU level: PoDIUM and EVENTS; on national level: LUKAS and AUTOtech.agil) and it a result of joint internally discussions and work across these	https://www.events-project.eu/ieee-sdf-mfi-conference-27-29-11-2023/

submitted in Combined SDF and IEEE MFI Conference	projects to improve our existing software framework for fusion and tracking	
Participated in SIS 60: Challenges of multi modal ML-based perception development & testing for automated driving applications	ROADVIEW, GAMMS and EVENTS projects participated in a Special Interest Session, moderated by EVENTS	https://www.events-project.eu/15th-its-european-congress-22-24-05-2023/
Participated in the 4th edition of the European Conference on Connected and Automated Driving (EUCAD2023)	Co-organised by FAME project . EVENTS was showcased in the exhibition area along with ROADVIEW and SUNRISE .	https://www.events-project.eu/4th-european-conference-on-connected-and-automated-driving-eucad-2023-03-04-05-2023/
Participated in the European Conference on Results from Research Projects on Road Transport (RTR Conference 2024)	EVENTS presented in a session moderated by CINEA along with EU projects CONNECT and SELFY . The event was also attended by representatives from PODIUM, SINFONICA, SUNRISE, FAME, AUGMENTED CCAM & MOVE2CCAM	https://www.events-project.eu/rtr-conference-2024-05-07-02-2024/
Participated in a survey	EVENTS participated in a survey released by FAME project	N/A
Participating in Horizon Results Booster	EVENTS along with SOTERIA, HEIDI, AI4CCAM and PHOEBE formulated a cluster and applied to HRB.	N/A
Liaison with a non-EU project	EVENTS along with ROADVIEW have been liaised with the Japanese SIP-Mobility Innovation Alliance project (#2)	Cooperation with the SIP Project #2 on the development of infrastructure and on-board sensor systems that utilize compact LIDAR technology to understand the situation of streets in living areas and busy districts

5.2 Networking activities with EU and international organisations

The main aim of EVENTS networking activities is to maximise the impact of the communication and dissemination of results amongst the relevant stakeholders. This enables the exchange of technical information and contributes to the dissemination of top-level, high-quality EU funding programmes and support European Research and Innovation Actions.

EVENTS partners seek every opportunity to discuss EVENTS developments within related organisations, associations, and networks where they already participate, and technical advances are presented in respective technical meetings and fora. Networking with relevant associations, organisations and European R&D initiatives is very important since this will ensure knowledge interchange between key actors and the adoption of proposed solutions.

In Table 10 below, a summary of the networking organisations, platforms, associations, agencies etc., (as detailed referenced in D7.1: EVENTS Communication, Dissemination, and social awareness, section 4.2) in which EVENTS disseminated its assets, shared knowledge and experience and mutually liaised, is depicted.

Table 10 Networking EU and international organisations

Networking party	Event	Link
CCAM Partnership	CCAM Multi-cluster meeting, 25.10.2022	https://www.events-project.eu/news-title-1/
European Commission, European Road Transport Research Advisory Council (ERTRAC) European Green Vehicles Initiative Association for the 2Zero partnership (EGVIAfor2Zero), Cooperative, Connected and Automated Mobility Association (CCAM Association)	RTR Conference 2023, 14-16.02.2023	https://www.events-project.eu/events-networking-at-ec-stand-in-rtr-2023-14-16-02-2023/
European Partnership on Connected, Cooperative and Automated Mobility (CCAM), European Commission, ERTICO	4 th European Conference on Connected and Automated Driving – EUCAD 2023, 03-04.05.2023	https://www.events-project.eu/4th-european-conference-on-connected-and-automated-driving-eucad-2023-03-04-05-2023/
ERTICO	15th ITS European Congress, 22-24.05.2023	https://www.events-project.eu/15th-its-european-congress-22-24-05-2023/
IEEE Intelligent Transportation Systems Society (ITSS)	26th IEEE International Conference on Intelligent Transportation Systems -ITSC 2023, 24-28.09.2023	https://www.events-project.eu/26th-ieee-international-conference-on-intelligent-transportation-systems-itsc-2023-24-28-09-2023/
Cooperative, Connected and Automated Mobility Association (CCAM Association)	RTR Conference 2024, 05-07.02.2024	https://www.events-project.eu/rtr-conference-2024-05-07-02-2024/

5.3 Planned activities

As far as the planned activities are concerned, EVENTS has scheduled the following activities:

- submitting 2 papers (jointly prepared by PoDIUM & EVENTS and by EVENTS, PoDIUM and the German project AUTotech.agil respectively) to the IEEE IV 2024 Conference.
- participating in Connecting Europe Days 2024 (application was accepted) with a shared booth with sister projects PoDIUM and ENVELOPE disseminating project’s recent outcomes with promotional materials.
- submitting a paper that has been accepted for poster presentation during Transportation Research Arena (TRA) 2024.

- submitting a SIS proposal, jointly with HEIDI, SOTERIA, AI4CCAM and PHOEBE for Transportation Research Arena (TRA) 2024.
- submitting an EoI, which it is accepted for being showcased on the Innovate UK exhibition stand, along with Hi Drive and ROADVIEW, at Transportation Research Arena (TRA 2024).
- participating in the 3rd Interactive Symposium on Research & Innovation for Connected and Automated Driving in Europe (EUCAD Symposium 2024) Networking Reception on Opening day, disseminating EVENTS project & networking with targeted stakeholders and CCAM projects.
- submitting 2 publications in the 35th IEEE Intelligent Vehicles Symposium.

6. EVENTS Social awareness

EVENTS, as part of its social innovation perspective, will thoroughly investigate possible ways to achieve its full potential and to benefit society. Social innovation in WP7 is inherently fed into EVENTS work plan, ensuring that societal aspects are always considered. More specifically, this will be achieved through EVENTS Task 7.4 on Social innovation & Gender Equality, which is going to be run during the last year of the project course (M24-M36).

The approach on both the social innovation and gender equality are depicted in D7.1 EVENTS Communication, Dissemination, and social awareness (section 5). The activities that will take place as part of Task 7.4, upon its commencement, will be thoroughly document in the next version of the current report, namely D7.4 Final EVENTS Communication, Dissemination, and social awareness (due in M36).

7. Evaluation & monitoring of activities

Measurable targets for communication and dissemination activities have been set, since the proposal phase, in order to ensure that the desired impact is achieved. In the context of close, effective, and efficient monitoring of the dissemination and communication activities, a KPI matrix has been developed, via using an excel spreadsheet, and it is regularly monitored. The KPI matrix is available on the internal project’s repository. It includes the KPIs’ names, along with their current value and the expected achieved results by the end of the project. The following Figure 8 presents the KPI matrix of M18 (February 2024) of the EVENTS project.

EVENTS Dissemination and Communication KPIs			
KPIs Names	Current values (M18)	Baseline value by the end of the project	Result
EVENTS brand identity (inc. logo, guidelines, templates, illustrations/graphics)	1	1	✓
Factsheet	1	1	✓
Standard presentation	1	1	✓
Brochure	1	2	✗
Poster	1	2	✗
Roll-up	1	2	✗
Project video	0	1	✗
E-newsletter	2	8	✗
e-Newsletter recipients	88	200	✗
Website	1	1	✓
Website visitors	1400	100	✓
Twitter account	1	1	✓
Twitter (members)	104	400	✗
LinkedIn account	1	1	✓
LinkedIn members	138	400	✗
Media articles	10	15	✗
Publications in Horizon Europe communication tools	3	5	✗
Media campaigns	1	1	✓
Advisory board members (total number)	9	6	✓
Advisory board members (members outside EU)	5	3	✓
Number of peer reviewed journal articles	1	5	✗
Conference publications	7	10	✗
Conference presentations	12	20	✗
Organisation of workshops/special sessions	1	4	✗
Number of international, EU and national projects networked	17	5	✓
Number of international, EU and national projects networked (outside EU)	1	2	✗
Number of liaison activities performed	8	6	✓
Number of liaison activities performed (outside EU)	1	4	✗
Number of discussions in fora, committees, associations & organisations	9	12	✗
Number of standardisation bodies and TCs networked	13	2	✓
Use case demonstrations	0	3	✗
Attendees per use case demonstration	0	30	✗
Final Event participants	0	120	✗

Figure 8 EVENTS KPIs monitoring matrix

8. Conclusions

The primary objective of this document is to provide a summary of the communication, dissemination, scientific, and liaison activities carried out in the initial 18 months of the EVENTS project.

The partners within the EVENTS consortium have been actively involved, playing a role in spreading the vision, results, and outcomes of EVENTS by participating in various events and producing materials such as press releases, technical documents, and scientific publications.

Valuable collaborations and synergies have been formed between EVENTS and other related projects and networks. These partnerships are viewed as mutually advantageous, with a shared goal of enhancing the dissemination of EVENTS project outcomes.

D.7.3: Intermediate EVENTS Communication, Dissemination, and social awareness is considered as a flexible and adaptive document to provide information about the status of the communication, dissemination, and scientific activities within EVENTS. Additional activities, which will take place by the end of the project will be reported in D7.4 Final EVENTS Communication, Dissemination, and social awareness (due in M36).

Disclaimer of Warranties

'This project has used a standard methodology already developed in MOSES project (Grant Agreement number: 861678), following EU recommendations. Ad hoc modifications were added to comply with the Grant Agreement conditions for EVENTS (Grant Agreement number: 101069614).'

References

- [1] Google Analytics, Dimensions and metrics: [GA4] Understand user metrics available at: <https://support.google.com/analytics/answer/12253918?hl=en> (Last Access 13/02/2024).
- [2] Communicating about your EU-funded project, available at: https://rea.ec.europa.eu/communicating-about-your-eu-funded-project_en (Last Access 13/02/2024).
- [3] EC Research & Innovation Participant Portal Glossary/Reference Terms, available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/support/glossary> (Last Access 13/02/2024).